

GLOBAL PROBLEMS AND THEIR THEORETICAL ANALYSIS, ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEMS

Boymurodova Khusniyabonu

Geography teacher of the 19th general secondary school, Shakhrisabz district, Kashkadarya region, 2nd category

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8395479>

Abstract. *In this article, the global environmental problems that have arisen before people in the world and their causes, as well as the solutions to the problems of analysis of global problems, the causes of their occurrence, the situations arising from their occurrence, and the issues of their elimination or prevention is spoken.*

Keywords: *ozone layer, skylob, greenhouse effect, hydrosphere, ozonosphere, ocean, freon gas, aluminum oxide, "skylob" station, atmosphere.*

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the socio-economic development of humanity has changed radically during the industrial and scientific-technical revolution in the world. As a result of these rapid changes, a number of environmental problems have arisen in the world, that is, in front of humanity. These environmental problems are the reason why such environmental problems are called global it affects all the processes taking place on our planet and living conditions of living organisms. Global problems are problems that have arisen with the development of society, pose a threat to humanity, and require the joint action of the world community to solve them.

The main types of global problems:

The problem of breaking the peace

Environmental problem

Demographic problem

The problem of energy supply

The problem of raw materials

Food problem

The problem of using the world's oceans

The problem of using space for peaceful purposes

The problem of eliminating the backlog, etc.

Peace and disarmament.

About 14,500 times, 3.5 billion people died in the war. In 1980, the countries of the world spent 1 trillion US dollars on armaments.

Environmental problem.

Ecological "garbage to space" carbon monoxide sulfate gas (fluorine gas, mole tooth, pomegranate flower in Tursunzoda) increasing SO₂ in the atmosphere increases the air temperature by 3-4 degrees. An increase in temperature by +2°C will cause the ice to melt more rapidly and the ocean level to rise by half a meter, as well as cause climate change.

Countries whose atmosphere is most polluted with carbon monoxide: Japan (2.9 thousand tons per 1 km² area), Germany (2.5), Great Britain (2.4), France (0.7), AKD1 (0, 5), Russia (0.1), China (0.3).

Demographic problem.

Online planning by UN. The growth of the world population will be 2% in 1960, 1.6% in 1980, 1.5% by the end of the century, 1.2% in 2100.

Problems of energy and raw materials.

The 1st reason for this problem is that the "appetite" of the world economy for energy and raw materials is increasing.

For example: 40% of all copper, 55% of iron, oil and natural gas, and 80% of bauxite mined in the 20th century are 20 years old.

- the reason is the limited number of checked reserves.
- the reason is that some regions and countries in the world are not provided with the same natural resources. For example: the Persian Gulf countries have 2/3 of the world's proven oil reserves. For example: 95% of GDP in Saudi Arabia comes from oil.

Food problem.

According to medical staff, the caloric medical norm of food consumed by a person should not be less than 2300-2600 kcal and 70-700g of oxygen per day. But according to the UN, only 1/100 of the world's population (developed countries) is provided with such food.

Italy ranks first in terms of food security per capita. And in Africa, Libya.

The food problem in developing countries is very complicated. 1/2 of the world's grain crops, 15-20% of meat, milk, and eggs are produced in these countries. For example: In Indonesia, Pakistan, meat consumption per capita is 4 kg (per year).

The problem of using the world's oceans

The comprehensive research and settlement of the world ocean caused the "World Ocean Problem".

Use of ocean biological resources to overcome the energy and raw materials problem. So far, the world's oceans provide 2% of human needs for food, and 12-15% of animal oxygen is taken from the ocean.

Rapid growth of international trade due to HGMT The volume of cargo transportation in the world's oceans is increasing.

Exclusion of developing countries is the biggest global problem. Currently, 40% of the population lives in poverty in the countries of Asia, Africa and Latin America. More than 70 countries import food products. Various diseases and child mortality are high due to poverty and hunger. "20th century plague" (SPID) is widespread in poor countries of tropical Africa.

One of the global environmental problems is the depletion of the ozone layer. The ozone layer is the shield of the earth's surface that traps ultraviolet rays from the sun. It is known that ultraviolet rays have a negative effect on living organisms on the surface of the earth. Like radiation burns and skin cancer in humans causes diseases. It seriously damages the productivity of grain crops.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Since the 50s of the 20th century, an increase in the amount of Freon gases (chlorine, fluorine, carbon) has been observed in the air. This began to destroy the ozone layer (ozonosphere) 25 km away. As a result, "Ozone hole" was formed. Ozone layer in the presence of oxygen, nitrogen oxides and other gases under the influence of sunlight, i.e. lightning formed and accumulated as a result of thunder and lightning.

Currently, a large amount of harmful substances and smoke are released into the atmosphere as a result of the widespread use of Freon gases, aviation gases and detonation of atomic bombs. This does not allow the ozone layer to accumulate.

A large amount of aluminum oxide is released into the atmosphere as a result of aviation and rocket launches. The released aluminum oxide is in the form of a white powder and prevents the sun's rays from reaching the earth's surface, and as a result, the sun's rays are reflected back. Rockets consume a lot of oxygen without polluting the atmosphere and affect the ozone layer.

The Saturn-5 rocket, launched by the US Skylob space station, created a 1800 km wide "hole" in the ionosphere, which filled up after 1.5 hours.

According to scientists' calculations, if 125 rockets similar to Saturn-5 are launched at the same time, they can destroy the ozone layer surrounding the earth's surface, and all living organisms on the earth's surface can die. Today, an ozone hole is formed in the atmosphere in the lower regions of Antarctica and Australia is expanding. A number of actions are being taken to prevent this situation. In 1981, the "Helsinki Declaration on the Protection of the Ozone Layer" was adopted by scientists, experts and statesmen of 81 countries, and measures to reduce the production of freon gases by the year 2000 were determined. As a result, the area of the ozone hole has been shrinking in recent years.

DISCUSSION

"Greenhouse Effect". In the following years, as a result of the increase of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere, the greenhouse effect was created. The reason for this is the widespread use of fuel products, especially coal, the use of fuels in vehicles, deforestation, and forest fires. These led to an acceleration of the greenhouse effect. If the situation continues like this, the temperature of the earth's surface may increase by 1.5-4.5 degrees by the 21st century. As a result, climate change, especially desertification, will increase.

Natural zones are shifting, ocean and sea levels are rising. Melting and shrinking glaciers such events occur. The problem of lack of fresh water. The role of water in the biosphere is huge. She is source of vitality and life. Although there is more than 1.5 billion cubic km of water in the hydrosphere, only 3% of it is fresh water. The main part of fresh water reserves is collected in polar ice caps. As society develops, the demand for fresh water is increasing. Fresh water makes up 3% of the total volume of the hydrosphere population, industry, and agriculture play a primary role in consumption. Fresh water is unevenly distributed over the surface of the earth. For example, 10% of the population of Africa is provided with regular fresh water, while in Europe this indicator is 95%. Especially in tropical African countries, the problem of clean drinking water is a serious problem is happening.

THE RESULT

Nowadays, the problem of fresh water shortage has become more acute under the influence of anthropogenic factors. Water used in some industries, household utilities and agriculture is discharged into rivers without treatment. As a result of this, along with river water pollution, various infectious diseases occur is coming The Rhine, Danube, Seine, Tiber, Mississippi, Volga, Dnieper, Don, Dniester, Nile, Ganga and other rivers are very polluted rivers. The world's oceans are also becoming more polluted. Ocean waters are especially polluted by oil products. More than 1/3 of the world's oceans are covered with an oil film. The oil film reduces evaporation, limits the development of plankton, ocean-atmosphere interactions. The Atlantic Ocean is the most polluted with oil.

CONCLUSION

All of the environmental problems mentioned above are related to anthropogenic, i.e., human factor. So what should we do? What measures should we take? Of course, humans are not limited to polluting nature. He is also taking measures to eliminate it. Environmental policy in many countries is being conducted. In our country, a solid legal framework has been created that regulates relations in the field of environmental protection and rational use of natural resources. In particular, the Republic of Uzbekistan article 50 of the Constitution states that "Citizens are obliged to take care of the natural environment".

Article 55 states that "Land, underground resources, water, flora and fauna and other natural resources are national resources, they must be used wisely, they are under state protection." In fact, nature has given us a gift by protecting the mother earth where we live it is the duty of each of us to use the blessings wisely, to keep the air we breathe clean.

REFERENCES

1. A. Sattorov, Q. Allanov, B. Abdumo'minov Global climate change, its consequences and adaptation to it. Termiz 2019.
2. Rafikov A., Vakhobov H., Kayumov A., Azimov Sh. Practical geography - T.: 2008.
3. Rafikov A.A., Khojimatov A.N., Alimkolov N.R., Kholmurodov Sh.A. Fundamentals of Geoecology - T.: 2015.
4. Пославская О.Ю. Геоморфология. Кашкадарьинская область. Том-1.- Ташкент, 1959. 142-173с.
5. Энциклопедический словарь географических терминов. М., 1968. 156с.
5. Когай Н.А. Туранская физико-географическая провинция. Науч. Тр. Т.: ТашГУ, 1969. 353-357с.
6. Маматов А.А. Қашкадарё вилояти географияси. -Қарши, 1994. 16-29б.